

A STUDY OF CONSOLIDATION EQUILIBRIUM IN COMPOSITES MADE BY FLEXIBLE INJECTION

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Keywords: *Liquid Composite Molding (LCM), Flexible Injection (FI), consolidation, void content*

1 General introduction

High performance composites made of continuous fibers and thermosetting resins are increasingly used in structural applications. However, it is well-known that composite manufacturing processes are prone to create porosity if not optimized properly [1, 2]. This can cause serious problems since even relatively minor void contents can reduce significantly the mechanical properties of the structure [3, 4]. Void formation during processing depends on the type of manufacturing method. For injection processes like Resin Transfer Molding (RTM), the quantity of voids is strongly dependent on the flow mechanisms during fiber bed impregnation [5, 6]. In autoclave processing, void content mainly depends on the consolidation pressure applied during cure [7, 8]. Minimization of void content has already been the subject of several previous works in the case of RTM [2, 9] and autoclave processing [3, 10]. In the present study, the issue of impregnation quality is investigated for a recently patented process called Flexible Injection (FI), which is currently implemented at École Polytechnique de Montréal to fabricate large structural composite parts.

2 Preliminary discussion

2.1 The Flexible Injection process

The main fabrication steps of Flexible Injection are schematically depicted in Fig. 1. The manufacturing setup is rather similar to that of RTM tooling except that a flexible membrane is placed between the two rigid parts of the mold. This membrane divides the cavity in two chambers: the bottom chamber contains the fibrous preform; the top chamber is initially empty (1). Starting from this initial configuration, a vacuum pressure is first applied in

both chambers. A controlled quantity of liquid thermoset resin is then injected in the lower chamber (2). After injection of the resin, the top chamber is filled with a pressurized incompressible fluid (called compaction fluid) in order to complete the impregnation of the fiber bed (3). Finally, the part is cured under constant pressure (4).

Flexible Injection (FI) provides a faster way to manufacture large structural composite parts than classical RTM by speeding up significantly the resin flow during the injection stage. Moreover, this technology permits to apply a constant pressure on the composite during the entire cure of the resin. These potential advantages come from the upper cavity that is deformed thanks to the flexible membrane throughout the manufacturing cycle. However, since the thickness of the injection cavity changes also during mold filling, the amount of resin injected must be carefully controlled in order to reach the desired fiber volume fraction in the final part.

Previous work demonstrated that Flexible Injection could be used to manufacture flat composite panels as well as relatively complex parts [11, 12]. It was notably shown that an appropriate selection of processing parameters led to a fairly uniform thickness profile in the final composite product. However, the performance of the process in terms of void content has not yet been fully evaluated.

As presented above, Flexible Injection shares common features with both RTM and autoclave processing. Dry fibers are first impregnated by the resin during resin and fluid injection. Then, a constant pressure is applied on the saturated preform to give its final shape to the composite. This important consolidation stage is detailed in the next section.

2.2 Consolidation equilibrium

Consolidation under a flexible cover takes place in other manufacturing techniques such as autoclave processing or Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI). Following the approach developed in Soil Mechanics, this phenomenon is usually described by Terzaghi's law:

$$P_c = \sigma_f + P_r \quad (1)$$

where P_c is the consolidation pressure (i.e., the compaction fluid pressure in the case of Flexible Injection), σ_f is the effective stress acting on the fibrous preform and P_r is the pressure in the resin. Note that the application of Terzaghi's equilibrium as presented in equation (1) to Flexible Injection implies two important hypotheses. Firstly, the membrane is assumed to be perfectly elastic with negligible rigidity so that the compaction pressure is completely transferred to the composite. Furthermore, the use of scalar quantities for the different parameters is only valid if consolidation equilibrium has been attained. Such assumption implies that the resin is uniformly distributed in the cavity and no resin flow occurs.

The term σ_f in equation (1) is strongly influenced by the fiber volume fraction V_f of the composite. Fig. 2 illustrates this by applying Terzaghi's law on the typical compaction curve of a fibrous preform. The compaction behavior of the fabric becomes then a key material property that determines the distribution of fiber stress and resin pressure during processing. As shown in Fig. 2, the equilibrium is influenced by two processing parameters: the compaction pressure P_c and the targeted fiber fraction V_f , which is directly driven by the amount of resin injected.

It is well known that engineering fabrics used in composite manufacturing possess a viscoelastic behavior. This means that the compaction response of the preform changes in time during processing. In practice, Terzaghi's equilibrium is valid until the state of the resin changes from liquid to solid rubbery. Consequently, the gel time of the resin is another processing parameter that affects the distribution of pressure inside the cavity. In certain cases, the gel time may also be too short to reach complete equilibrium. The resulting final part is then likely to exhibit local heterogeneity such as thickness variations for example.

Maintaining sufficient resin pressure until gel time is a key issue to ensure low porosity in the final part. The different parameters discussed above are likely to influence the void content in the composite by affecting the pressure equilibrium. Finally, another important factor is the vacuum pressure P_v applied in the injection chamber before processing. As in other processes, this parameter will affect the size of the air bubbles created at the flow front during filling of the cavity and may consequently exert an influence on the final void content.

2.3 Research objectives

This study aims to characterize the impact of process and material dependent parameters on the impregnation quality and the consolidation equilibrium during Flexible Injection. The goal is to assess the performance of the process in terms of void content and determine processing conditions that lead to acceptable levels of porosity. For that purpose, two series of flat composite panels were fabricated in the laboratory. The first series focuses on identifying the processing parameters that govern the impregnation quality. The second experimental plan is a preliminary study on preforming used as a tool for process optimization. The potential benefits of preforming, such as the improvement of resin impregnation and the modification of compaction behavior, will be discussed in the sequel.

3 Experimental setup and materials

3.1 Materials

Parts were fabricated with a diglycidylether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy cured with an anhydride hardener. This resin was selected because of its important reactivity when processed at high temperature. A few minutes are necessary to yield complete cure at 140°C. Such processing conditions will help determine if proper impregnation can be achieved in extremely short manufacturing times. The reinforcement was an E-glass quasi-unidirectional fabric Saeruni from Saertex.

3.2 Manufacturing setup

The mold used for this study has a rectangular cavity of 142 mm x 410 mm. Thicknesses of the different chambers are 6.5 mm for the injection cavity (h_{inj} in Fig. 1) and 3 mm for the compaction cavity (h_{comp} in Fig. 1). The mold is equipped with sensors for measuring the compaction pressure and the resin

pressure at the injection gate and vent. Prior to injection, the tooling was heated with electrical plates to ensure a temperature of 140°C inside the cavity.

Resin was injected at room temperature with a pneumatic gun that allows a precise control of the injected quantity. A specially devised machine was used to inject the compaction fluid. The fluid was pre-heated at 100°C before injection in order to avoid any significant cooling of the mold. The compaction machine was controlled by a Labview program that records the pressure measured by the different sensors. After filling of the compaction cavity, a constant pressure was finally imposed on the fluid during the entire consolidation stage.

4 Manufacturing with non-preformed fabric

Previous studies on Flexible Injection involved spraying a small amount of reactive binder on the fibers to prepare semi-rigid preforms. It was observed that such procedure improved the thickness uniformity of the final part and limited the creation of processing defects in strongly curved sections [13]. However, preforming of the fiber bed introduces an additional manufacturing step and can be viewed as an impediment to shorten cycle time. Consequently, the fabrications of the first experimental plan were carried out using raw, non-preformed reinforcement in order to evaluate the influence of process parameters on the pressure distribution inside the mold. Moreover, the results obtained will help verify if preforming is a necessary step for an effective implementation of Flexible Injection.

4.1 Experimental plan

The first experimental plan included the fabrication of 10 test specimens. The processing parameters are summarized in Table 1. Three parameters were investigated: the fiber volume fraction, the compaction pressure and the vacuum pressure applied in the cavity. The influence of these factors on the consolidation equilibrium was evaluated by studying the pressure evolution during processing. After demolding, visual inspection and void content analysis were conducted to assess the impact of processing conditions on the overall impregnation quality of the composite.

4.2 Pressure analysis

Fig. 3 shows the pressure profiles recorded during a typical experiment (in this example, fabrication of part 2). Injection of the resin corresponds to the temporary increase of inlet pressure visible between 10 to 20 seconds. Injection of the compaction fluid begins 10 seconds later. After filling of the compaction cavity (around 35 s), the compaction pressure is raised to 600 kPa. As this stage is manually controlled, a small adjustment is necessary around 80 seconds to maintain the desired pressure. As seen in Fig. 3, this changes instantaneously the resin pressure and shows that the resin is still liquid inside the mold. At 90 seconds, the resin pressure at the vent starts decreasing whereas the compaction pressure is kept constant. This observation indicates that the resin has gelled at the vent location. This phenomenon occurs later (around 130 s) at the injection gate. This difference is not surprising since the resin particles located at the inlet and near the vent exhibit different thermal histories.

To estimate the consolidation equilibrium before solidification of the resin, the resin pressure at gel P_r was calculated as an averaged value on a 5-second interval before the gel time. Knowing the compaction pressure P_c , it was finally possible to estimate the effective stress of the fibers σ_f according to Terzaghi's law (1).

4.3 Visual inspection

Based on past experience on the process, the experimental plan was started with the following parameters: $V_f = 58\%$, $P_c = 600$ kPa and full vacuum (part 2). Fig. 4 shows that the part is visually correct. Nevertheless, when increasing V_f , a manufacturing defect appeared on the fabricated specimens. As shown in Fig. 5, a dry spot of non-impregnated fibers is visible near the vent port of the panel. Note that the case presented here (i.e. part 7) is the worst result obtained and that some of samples (part 2 and 3) did not exhibit any important defect.

To explain the creation of the dry zone, the specific filling pattern associated with Flexible Injection must be discussed (see Fig. 1). The originality of the process relies on a two stage impregnation of the fiber bed: resin flows above the preform during stage 2, followed by through-thickness wetting of the fibers during stage 3. In practice, this is ensured by the compaction fluid which deforms the membrane in a wavelike manner (step 3) and pushes the resin towards the vent and inside the preform at

the same time. However, this desired filling pattern may not always be possible when using a non-preformed fiber bed. As a matter of fact, the natural fiber volume fraction of the fiber plies is relatively low (around 37 % which corresponds to a 9 mm thickness). Therefore, the open gap between the membrane and the top mold is likely to be very narrow once the mold is closed. With such a configuration, the resin will mostly impregnate the fibers during the injection stage. When the compaction fluid is injected, the progression of the resin towards the vent becomes then slower than expected. Consequently, the compaction fluid front may overlap the resin front. At this stage, resin has to impregnate the fabric longitudinally as in RTM. Moreover, the rest of the dry fabric is compacted by the compaction fluid, thus inducing a large drop in the permeability of the fiber bed. Important edge effects are then likely to occur at the end of mold filling. Once the preferential flow channels are filled, the resin exits the mold and the vent is clamped. A non-impregnated zone is thus created in the region close to the vent outlet.

After closing of the vent, pressure is applied on the resin so that it will continue to flow in the unsaturated region. However, the impregnation of the preform is not completed since a dry spot exists on the final part. Two hypotheses can be formulated to explain this observation:

- At some point, the air pressure in the dry zone equals the resin pressure and the flow stops.
- Pressure equilibrium is not reached before gel.

The mechanisms of dry sport creation are discussed in the next section by analyzing the size of the defects observed for different manufacturing conditions.

4.4 Analysis of dry spot size

To estimate the dry spot size, pictures of the plates were taken with a standard reflex camera. A hard light source was placed behind the specimen to increase the contrast at the boundary of the non-impregnated zone. The images were analyzed with an edge detection program developed with Matlab. The surface calculated by this program was finally multiplied by the measured thickness of the part to give the dry spot volume as reported in Table 1.

In Fig. 6, the dry spot volume is plotted versus the resin pressure at gel time. As expected, the size of the dry zone decreases with resin pressure. Moreover, the defect is eliminated for a resin

pressure above 500 kPa. Two process parameters have a direct influence on resin pressure: the fiber volume fraction V_f and the compaction pressure P_c . At fixed V_f , increasing the compaction pressure will increase resin pressure. This is illustrated by parts 1, 2 and 3 respectively manufactured with $P_c = 200, 600$ and 1000 kPa. A dry spot exists in part 1, whereas no defect is detected in parts 2 and 3. This shows that for a fiber volume fraction of 58%, the compaction pressure has to be between 200 and 600 kPa to create a sufficient resin pressure in order to prevent the apparition of dry spots in the final part.

For a fixed compaction pressure, the resin pressure will be a direct function of V_f . In fact, increasing the fiber volume fraction will have three consequences that may affect the dry spot size:

- decrease in P_r ;
- increase of the initial dry spot size after closing the vent (due to a lower quantity of resin injected);
- reduction of fabric permeability that may slow the impregnation after passing over the resin front by the compaction fluid front.

As these three consequences promote the creation of larger dry spots, it appears that decreasing V_f is the only possible way to eliminate the dry spot if the compaction pressure is limited to a maximum value.

The vacuum pressure P_v is also expected to affect the size of the dry zone since it represents the pressure inside the cavity when the defect is created (i.e., when the vent is closed). Fig. 7 shows the size of the dry spot observed on three parts fabricated at an expected V_f of 62 %, with complete vacuum (-95 kPa), half vacuum (-50 kPa) and without vacuum in the injection chamber. As expected, the dry sport is smaller for a more complete vacuum. It is also interesting to note that the resin pressure is correlated to the final size of the dry spot. Since the quantity of injected resin is constant, a larger dry spot implies a lower fiber volume fraction in the impregnated zone. As a result, the consolidation equilibrium is modified and P_r increases as shown in Fig. 7.

Finally, the influence of gel time was studied by decreasing the amount of catalyst mixed with the resin. This new formulation resulted in an increase of the gel time from 80 seconds to 270 seconds. Two parts were reproduced with this resin: part 9 similar to part 5 which had a dry spot of normal size and part 10 similar to 7 and exhibiting the biggest defect. In the first case, the dry sport has completely

disappeared and the part seems well impregnated. In the second case, only a tiny dry area remains visible. This defect concerns a few fiber bundles which seem to be partially saturated and its size is too small to be quantified by the image analysis program. These observations prove that a longer gel time permits to reduce the formation of dry spots. Consequently, the hypothesis stating that pressure equilibrium exists between the resin and the air contained in the dry spot can be refuted. With the recommended resin formulation used for parts 1 to 8, the gel time is indeed too short to reach pressure equilibrium in the mold cavity.

4.5 Void content analysis

Except for the dry spot, no visible defects were detected in the rest of the panels. A matrix digestion procedure based on pyrolysis was used to characterize the impregnation quality in this apparently well-impregnated zone. Each part were cut to remove the dry zone when needed and 3 samples of dimensions 25 mm × 25 mm were taken in the composite plate (one on each side and the third one in the middle). Void content and fiber volume fraction of these samples were estimated according to norm ASTM D2734.

For parts fabricated under full vacuum and $P_c = 600$ kPa, the measured fiber volume fraction is reported in Fig. 8 according to the effective stress estimated from Terzaghi's law. The results are representative of a typical compaction behavior and can be interpolated by a classical power law model (solid line in Fig. 8):

$$\sigma_f = A \cdot V_f^B \quad (2)$$

As already mentioned, the compaction response of an engineering fabric depends strongly on time. The behavior of the fiber bed can also be sensitive to other factors such as temperature or lubrication induced by resin saturation. As a consequence, the compaction behavior characterized by compression tests on a regular testing machine may not always be representative of the real process. In that sense, the compaction curve of Fig. 8 is particularly interesting since it represents the actual processing behavior.

For parts fabricated under full vacuum, the evolution of void content with resin pressure P_r shows the expected behavior in Fig. 9, i.e., increasing P_r tends to reduce the void content. Note that all measured void contents are under 1% with standard deviations

under 0.1%, i.e., the quality of the specimens is quite uniform.

5 Fabric preforming

As mentioned earlier, previous investigations on Flexible Injection showed that the use of preformed fabrics brought many advantages in terms of process implementation and final quality. For example, preforming facilitates the handling of the fiber bed and prevents fiber wash-out during injection. However, in-depth knowledge of the impact of preforming on the physical phenomena taking place during manufacturing still needs to be developed.

5.1 Expected advantages and drawbacks

In a previous study on curved part manufacturing by Flexible Injection, it was shown that the use of a preforming binder has an influence on the mechanical response of the reinforcement [13]. Two main advantages brought by preforming can be deduced from this preliminary work. Firstly, preforming allows increasing the natural fiber volume fraction of the fabric. In the case studied here, reducing the thickness of the fiber bed enhances the resin flow in the cavity as well as the injection of the compaction fluid. Indeed, a larger free space is created between the preform and the top mold. Such configuration should promote flow in the open gap followed by through-thickness impregnation and result in a more uniform resin distribution. Secondly, preforming changes the compaction behavior of the fabric. This effect is illustrated schematically in Fig. 10, which shows a shift of the compaction curve induced by preforming. Such modification can give many advantages during manufacturing. For example, for a targeted V_f of 60% and a fixed compaction pressure P_c , preforming rises the resin pressure P_r . Inversely, if P_r is sufficient, then preforming allows processing at a higher V_f or a lower P_c . In an industrial application, lowering P_c can substantially reduce tooling costs.

However, it is important not to forget that preforming can have a negative impact on process performance. One of the main drawbacks during the resin flow stage lies in the decrease of permeability due to compaction. In addition, the spatial distribution of the preforming binder must be as uniform as possible to avoid local thickness and permeability variations. Finally, the presence of a

binder can result in a lower mechanical performance. In particular, the matrix-binder interface must not create local weakness in the composite structure.

5.2 Preforming procedure

Fibrous preforms were prepared by manually spraying a liquid thermoset binder on both sides of each fabric ply with a paint gun. The stacking was then compressed to a desired preforming thickness between rigid plates until cure of the binder. Two types of binder were used in the study: the epoxy resin used for manufacturing and a peroxide cured vinylester resin. When using the epoxy binder, the plates of the press were heated to 140°C, whereas the preforms containing the vinylester binder were prepared at room temperature. In all cases, the quantity of binder represented approximately 1% of the fiber total weight.

5.3 Results on a compression testing machine

Compaction tests were conducted to characterize the fabric behavior and show the influence of preforming. Samples of 50 mm × 50 mm consisting of 9 fabric plies were compressed with an INSTRON testing machine equipped with parallel plates. The experiments were carried out at room temperature using the following test sequence:

- constant speed compaction at 10 mm/min from natural thickness to the desired fiber volume fraction for the test $V_{f,t}$;
- relaxation at $V_{f,t}$ during 30 min ;
- decompaction at 10 mm/min.

Large preforms were first prepared with the epoxy binder. Three preforming fiber volume fractions $V_{f,p}$ were used during the preforming operation. Smaller samples were cut out of the preforms and tested as described above together with non preformed specimens. The following ranges of fiber volume fraction were investigated during the tests:

- $V_{f,t} = 56-72$ % for non preformed fabrics
- $V_{f,t} = 56-66$ % for preforms at $V_{f,p} = 61$ %
- $V_{f,t} = 60-68$ % for preforms at $V_{f,p} = 64.6$ %
- $V_{f,t} = 66-72$ % for preforms at $V_{f,p} = 70.1$ %

Each compaction test was repeated three times.

The effective stress measured after 80 seconds of relaxation was used to estimate the compaction of the fiber bed at gel time. Results are reported in Fig. 11 for the raw fibrous reinforcement and for a preform prepared at $V_{f,p} = 61$ %. Solid lines were obtained by fitting the experimental data with the

power law model (2). As observed in Fig. 11, the two compaction curves cross each other close to the preforming fiber fraction $V_{f,p}$. For fiber volume fractions lower than $V_{f,p}$ the preform is easier to compact than the raw material. On the other hand, the preform becomes more rigid when the fiber fraction exceeds $V_{f,p}$. This observation tends to confirm previously obtained results reported in Causse et al. [13].

As shown in Fig. 12, the same behavior is observed for other preforming conditions. Note that for sake of clarity, this figure only plots the power law model. Fig. 12 clearly shows that preforming can have a beneficial effect on the processing quality. Indeed, preforming at a fiber volume fraction $V_{f,p}$ higher than that of the final part will increase resin pressure during manufacturing compared to a non preformed reinforcement. However, the preforming stage can become detrimental if the targeted V_f of the final part is higher than $V_{f,p}$.

5.4 Manufacturing experiments

As already discussed, compaction results obtained with a testing machine may not be perfectly representative of a real manufacturing process. Moreover, some potential drawbacks such as a decrease in permeability cannot be studied with a compression testing machine. In order to verify the positive impact of preforming on the pressure distribution in the cavity, four test parts were manufactured with preformed fiber beds. Preforming and processing conditions used during this second series of fabrications are reported in Table 2. All the experiments were conducted with full vacuum pressure.

Fig. 13 shows the effective stress deduced from the pressure distribution recorded during manufacturing. As can be seen, all data points are located under the compaction curve obtained with non preformed fabrics. This confirms that preforming allows increasing resin pressure during processing by modifying the compaction behavior of the reinforcement.

By decreasing the natural thickness of the fiber stacking, it was also expected that preforming could modify the filling pattern and eventually eliminate the dry spot. However, visual inspection of parts 11 to 13 revealed another type of impregnation issue. As shown in Fig. 14, parts fabricated with the epoxy binder possess a very poor visual aspect. These defects are not full dry zones, but look like regions

of low saturation. A possible explanation of this behavior is connected with the binder, which may locally prevent the impregnation of the fiber bundles. This problem could be caused by the low viscosity of the epoxy binder at the high temperature imposed during preforming. Under such conditions, the binder may migrate into the fiber bundle and subsequently hinder fiber wetting at the microscopic scale.

In order to investigate this possibility, the last test part was manufactured with a vinylester binder, which remains more viscous during the preforming stage. Fig. 15. shows that the resulting part exhibits a good surface appearance. Finally, it is interesting to note that the dry spot has also been completely eliminated. This suggests that a more uniform resin distribution at the end of the filling stage can indeed be achieved when working with preformed fabrics.

6 Conclusion

This study investigated the performance of Flexible Injection (FI) for fast processing of high performance composites. An experimental setup was first devised for high temperature fabrication of composite panels with a short cycle time. The mold was instrumented with pressure sensors to study the consolidation equilibrium that takes place during processing. A series of test parts were fabricated for various manufacturing conditions using non preformed fabrics. As predicted by Terzaghi's law, the resin pressure recorded during processing is strongly influenced by the compaction pressure and the fiber volume fraction of the final part.

Void content analysis showed a low and decreasing level of porosity when the resin pressure increases. However, an important defect in the form of a dry spot near the vent is present in some specimens. This manufacturing default was attributed to an inappropriate filling pattern and premature gel of the resin. Additional experiments conducted with preformed fiber beds showed that preforming could eliminate this defect. Furthermore, compression tests were carried out to evaluate the impact of preforming on the compaction behavior. Results indicate that preforming can be used to tailor the mechanical response of the fabric and eventually modify the consolidation equilibrium during processing.

Table 1. Description of the parts fabricated without preforming (* stands for a long gel time resin)

Part number	V_f (%)	P_c ($\times 100^* \text{kPa}$)	P_v (kPa)	Dry spot size (cm^3)
1	58	2	-95	2.9
2	58	6	-95	0
3	58	10	-95	0
4	60	6	-95	0.4
5	62	6	-95	1.0
6	62	6	-50	6.7
7	62	6	0	9.8
8	64	6	-95	3.8
9*	60	6	-95	0
10*	62	6	0	0

Table 2. Description of the parts fabricated after preforming

Part number	V_f (%)	P_c ($\times 100 \text{kPa}$)	Binder type	$V_{f,p}$ (%)
11	60	6	epoxy	61
12	62	6	epoxy	64.6
13	66	6	epoxy	70.1
14	60	6	vinylester	61

Fig. 1. Description of Flexible Injection (FI).

Fig. 2. Illustration of Terzaghi's law on the typical compaction curve of a fibrous reinforcement.

Fig. 3. Typical pressure evolutions measured in time during Flexible Injection.

Fig. 4. Photograph of part 2 ($V_f = 58\%$, complete vacuum and $P_c = 6$ bars).

Fig. 5. Photograph of part 7 ($V_f = 62\%$, no vacuum and $P_c = 6$ bars) showing an important dry spot close to the vent.

Fig. 6. Evolution of dry spot volume with resin pressure P_r .

Fig. 9. Evolution of void content with resin pressure P_r .

Fig. 7. Influence of vacuum pressure P_v on dry spot volume and resin pressure.

Fig. 8. Compaction curve obtained from fabrication data.

Fig. 10. Schematic illustration of the effect of preforming on the consolidation equilibrium.

Fig. 11. Influence of preforming on the compaction behavior characterized with a testing machine.

Fig. 12. Influence of preforming conditions on the compaction behavior.

Fig. 13. Effect of preforming as observed from fabrication data.

Fig. 14. Comparison of parts fabricated at $V_f = 60\%$ without preforming (up, part 4) and with preforming at $V_{fp} = 61\%$ with epoxy binder (down, part 11).

Fig. 15. Comparison of parts fabricated at $V_f = 60\%$ with preforming at $V_{fp} = 61\%$ with epoxy binder (up, part 11) and vinylester binder (down, part 14).

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